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PERMUTATION GROUPS IN MAGMA

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ABSTRACT

Groups arise in several different categories in Magma. In the case of the category of permutation groups and the category of soluble groups defined by a power-conjugate presentation, all groups in the category are finite. However, the finitely-presented group category, the polycyclic group category, the abelian group category and the matrix group category contain both finite and infinite groups. In the case of the abelian group category and the matrix group category, a large number of functions are available for finite groups only. In the near future, these functions will be extended to finite finitely-presented groups of moderate order.

In this paper we discuss the group of permutations, solve some problems that are only available for finite groups.

Keywords: Magma, groups, Permutation groups, Matrix groups, Polycyclic groups, Automorphism, system, Databases, Abelian groups, Homomorphisms, graph.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Группы возникают в нескольких различных категориях в Magma. В случае категории групп подстановок и категории разрешимых групп, определенных степенно-сопряженным представлением, все группы в категории конечны. Однако категория конечно представленной группы, категория полициклической группы, категория абелевой группы и категория матричной группы содержат как конечные, так и бесконечные группы. В случае абелевой групповой категории и матричной групповой категории большое количество функций

доступно только для конечных групп. В ближайшем будущем эти функции будут распространены на конечные конечно определенные группы среднего порядка. В этой статье мы обсуждаем группу перестановок, решаем некоторые проблемы, которые доступны только для конечных групп.

Ключевые слова: Магма, группы, группы перестановок, группы матриц, полициклические группы, автоморфизм, система, базы данных, абелевы группы, гомоморфизмы, граф.

ANATATSIYA

Guruhlar magmada bir nechta turli toifalarda paydo bo'ladi. Permutatsiya guruhlari toifasi va kuch-konjugat taqdimoti bilan aniqlangan eruvchan guruhlar toifasi bo'lsa, toifadagi barcha guruhlar cheklangan. Biroq, cheklangan taqdim etilgan guruh toifasi, politsiklik guruh toifasi, abelian guruh toifasi va matritsali guruh toifasi ham chekli, ham cheksiz guruhlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Abel guruhlari toifasi va matritsalar guruhi toifalari holatida ko'p sonli funktsiyalar faqat cheklangan guruhlar uchun mavjud. Yaqin kelajakda bu funktsiyalar o'rtacha tartibli cheklangan cheklangan guruhlariga kengaytiriladi.

Ushbu maqolada biz almashtirishlar guruhini muhokama qilamiz, faqat cheklangan guruhlar uchun mavjud bo'lgan ba'zi muammolarni hal qilamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Magma, guruhlar, Permutatsiya guruhlari, Matritsa guruhlari, Politsiklik guruhlar, Avtomorfizm, tizim, Ma'lumotlar bazalari, Abel guruhlari, Gomomorfizmlar, grafik.

Introduction

In Magma, we can work with several categories of finite (or infinite) groups, as, for instance

Permutation groups : GrpPerm;

Matrix groups: GrpMat;

Polycyclic groups : GrpPC;

Abelian groups (also infinite) : GrpAb;

Finitely presented groups: GrpFP;

Construction and Actions Magma contains a large amount of machinery for dealing with permutation groups of finite degree. The following list summarises various constructions of these groups available in Magma.

Permutation representations for classical groups, e.g. $PGL(n, q)$, $PSp(n, q)$,

$PSU(n, q^2)$, $P\Omega(n, q)$

Construction of wreath products with both types of action

Orbits on points, sets of points, and sequences of points

Systems of imprimitivity

Induced actions on G – sets

Base and strong generating set: Sims-Schreier algorithm, random Schreier algorithm, Todd-Coxeter Schreier algorithm, Brownie-Cannon-Sims verification

Stabilizer of a point, set of points, sequence of points, partition

Automorphism groups of graphs, codes and designs

Homomorphisms induced by actions on orbits and systems of imprimitivity

Random element generation: Holt-Leedham-Green-O'Brien algorithm

Databases: Transitive groups up to degree 15 (Butler), primitive groups up to degree 50 (Sims), irreducible soluble subgroups of $GL(n, p)$ for $p^n < 256$ (Short), simple groups up to order a million (Campbell and Robertson), sporadic simple groups

PRELIMINARIES.

A permutation group G is a group of bijections $X \rightarrow X$, for some set X . The group G is said to act on X and the elements of G are called permutations (of the set X). A given permutation group G may have actions on sets other than the one on which it is defined. Thus, any set upon which G has a legitimate action will be called a G -set. The set X is called the natural G -set for the group G ,

and the action of G on X is called the natural action of G . Note that the group G also has a natural induced action on the G -closure of any derived set of X . Magma expects the G -set X to be of finite cardinality n . The elements of a G -set are called points. Let Y be a G -set for G . The subset of Y whose points are fixed by every permutation of G , is called the fixed-point set for G , while the subset of Y consisting of points moved by some permutation of G is called the support of G . Similarly, for an element g of G the fixed-point set and the support of g are, respectively, the subsets of Y consisting of the points fixed and moved by g . The degree of G is defined to be the cardinality of the natural G -set of G ; whereas the degree of an element g of G is defined to be the cardinality of the support of g , i.e. the number of points moved by g . Permutation groups in Magma are limited to degree less than 2^{30} .

The Category of Permutation Groups - The family of all permutation groups of finite degree forms a category. The objects are the permutation groups and the morphisms are group homomorphisms. The Magma designation for this category of permutation groups is GrpPerm. The Construction of a Permutation Group Every permutation group acting on a set X is created as a subgroup of the symmetric group $\text{Sym}(X)$. Thus, the construction of a general permutation group is a two-step process:

- (i) The appropriate symmetric group, $\text{Sym}(X)$, is constructed;
- (ii) The required group G is then defined as a subgroup of $\text{Sym}(X)$.

For convenience, a constructor `PermutationGroup<...>`, which combines these two steps, is provided.

MAIN PART.

Construction of the Symmetric Group: `SymmetricGroup(n)` - Given an integer $n \geq 1$, create the generic permutation group acting on the natural G -set

$\Omega = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, i.e. the symmetric group $\text{Sym}(\Omega)$. Initially, only a structure

table is created for $\text{Sym}(n)$, so that, in particular, generators are not defined. This function is normally used to provide a context for the creation of elements and subgroups of $\text{Sym}(n)$. If structural computation is attempted with the group created by $\text{Sym}(n)$, then generators will be created dynamically.

`SymmetricGroup(X)` - Given a finite set X of cardinality $n \geq 1$, create the generic group G of permutations of X – the symmetric group $\text{Sym}(X)$. Initially, only a structure table is created for $\text{Sym}(X)$, so that, in particular, generators are not defined. This function is normally used to provide a context for the creation of elements and subgroups of $\text{Sym}(X)$. If structural computation is attempted with the group created by $\text{Sym}(X)$, then generators will be created dynamically. Although the group G is defined on the set X , G is represented internally as a group of permutations of the set $\Omega = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Translation between X and Ω is done at input/output time. The precise representation can be found by using the Labelling function. If X is an indexed set then the indexing of elements of X determines the correspondence. `StandardGroup(G)` - Return a group H isomorphic to G , but acting on the standard set $\{1, \dots, n\}$. This function is useful when the natural G -set for G is not the standard set. If the natural G -set for G is the standard set, G is returned. The isomorphism from G to H is also returned.

Example 1. We define the symmetric group on the set of strings

```
({ "a", "b", "c", "d", "e", "f", "g" });
S := Sym({ "a", "b", "c", "d", "e", "f", "g" });
S;
GSet(S); →Symmetric group S acting on a set of cardinality 7
Order = 5040 = 2^4 * 3^2 * 5 * 7
GSet{@ c, f, b, e, a, d, g @}
```

We define the symmetric group of degree 10 acting on the set $\{0, 1, \dots, 9\}$.

```
G := Sym({ 0..9 });
G;
GSet(G); → Symmetric group G acting on a set of cardinality 10
Order = 3628800 = 2^8 * 3^4 * 5^2 * 7
GSet{@ 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 @}
```

Construction of a Permutation: `elt<G | L >` - Given a permutation group G defined as acting on the set $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ of cardinality $n \geq 1$, and a list L of distinct elements a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n of X , construct the element g of G defined by

$x_i \rightarrow a_i$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Unless G is known to be the generic permutation group of degree n , the permutation will be tested for membership of G , and if g is not an element of G , the function will fail. If g does lie in G , g will have G as its parent. Since the membership test may involve constructing a base and strong generating set for G , this constructor may occasionally be very costly. Hence, a permutation g should be defined as an element of a subgroup of the generic group only when membership of G is required by subsequent operations involving g .

`G ! Q` - Given a permutation group G defined as acting on the set $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ of cardinality $n \geq 1$, and a sequence $Q = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n]$ of distinct elements of X , construct the permutation g of X defined by $x_i \rightarrow a_i$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$. This permutation will have G as its parent structure. As in the case of the `elt` constructor, the operation will fail if g is not an element of G and the same observations concerning the cost of membership testing apply.

`G ! (...)(...)(...)` - Given a permutation group G defined as acting on the set $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, construct the permutation g corresponding to the given product of cycles. Adjacent letters must be separated by commas. Further, cycles of length one must be omitted. The coercion operator `!` may be omitted only within the context of the standard constructors `sub<>`, `ncl<>` and `quo<>`. Once the permutation g has been constructed, it will be tested for membership in G . If it is not a member, the construction fails.

Construct the identity permutation in the permutation group G .

The three different constructions are illustrated by the following code, which assigns to each of the variables x , y and z the permutation $(1)(2,3)(4,5,6)$.

```
S6 := Sym(6);
x := elt<S6 | 1,3,2,5,6,4>;
x; →(2, 3)(4, 5, 6)
y := S6![1,3,2,5,6,4];
y; →(2, 3)(4, 5, 6)
z := S6!(2,3)(4,5,6);
z; →(2, 3)(4, 5, 6)
S6!1; →Id(S6)
```

Construction of a General Permutation Group: `PermutationGroup< X | L >` - Suppose that the cardinality of the set X is n . Construct the permutation group G acting on the set X generated by the permutations defined by the list L . A term of the list L must be an object of one of the following types:

1. A sequence of n elements of X defining a permutation of X (note that this is only well-defined when X is an indexed set);
2. A set or sequence of sequences of type (1);
3. An element of $\text{Sym}(X)$;
4. A set or sequence of elements of $\text{Sym}(X)$;
5. A subgroup of $\text{Sym}(X)$;
6. A set or sequence of subgroups of $\text{Sym}(X)$.

Each element or group specified by the list must belong to the same generic permutation group. The group G will be constructed as a subgroup of some group which contains each of the elements and groups specified in the list. The generators of G consist of the elements specified by the terms of the list L together with the stored generators for groups specified by terms of the list. The `PermutationGroup` constructor is shorthand for the two statements:

`SX := Sym(X); G := sub< SX | L >`; where `sub< ... >` is the subgroup constructor described in the next subsection.

PermutationGroup< n | L > - Construct the permutation group G acting on the set $X = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ generated by the permutations defined by the list L. The possibilities for the terms of the list L are the same as for the constructor PermutationGroup< X | L >.

Example 2. The Hessian group generated by the permutations (1, 2, 4)(5, 6, 8)(3, 9, 7) and (4, 5, 6)(7, 9, 8) may be created by the statement:

```
H := PermutationGroup< 9 | (1,2,4)(5,6,8)(3,9,7), (4,5,6)(7,9,8) >;
```

H; → Permutation group H acting on a set of cardinality 9

```
(1, 2, 4)(3, 9, 7)(5, 6, 8)
(4, 5, 6)(7, 9, 8)
```

Consider the group G of order 648 generated by the permutations (1,6,7)(2,5,8,3,4,9)(11,12) and (1,3)(4,9,12)(5,8,10,6,7,11).

```
G := PermutationGroup< 12 | (1,6,7)(2,5,8,3,4,9)(11,12),
(1,3)(4,9,12)(5,8,10,6,7,11) >;
```

G; → Permutation group G acting on a set of cardinality 12

```
(1, 6, 7)(2, 5, 8, 3, 4, 9)(11, 12)
```

```
(1, 3)(4, 9, 12)(5, 8, 10, 6, 7, 11)
```

G.1; →(1, 6, 7)(2, 5, 8, 3, 4, 9)(11, 12)

G.1*G.2; →(1, 7, 3, 9, 2, 8)(4, 12, 5, 10, 6, 11)

Degree(G); →12

GSet(G); →GSet{@ 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 @}

Generic(G); →Symmetric group acting on a set of cardinality 12

Order = 479001600 = $2^{10} * 3^5 * 5^2 * 7 * 11$

Generators(G); →{ (1, 6, 7)(2, 5, 8, 3, 4, 9)(11, 12),

```
(1, 3)(4, 9, 12)(5, 8, 10, 6, 7, 11)}
```

Ngens(G); →2

x := G ! (1,6,7)(2,5,8,3,4,9)(11,12);

x; →(1, 6, 7)(2, 5, 8, 3, 4, 9)(11, 12)

Parent(x); →Permutation group G acting on a set of cardinality 12

Order = 648 = $2^3 * 3^4$

```
(1, 6, 7)(2, 5, 8, 3, 4, 9)(11, 12)
```

```
(1, 3)(4, 9, 12)(5, 8, 10, 6, 7, 11)
```

We determine the orders of those subgroups of the Mathieu group M_{24} which are perfect but not simple. We use the function PerfectSubgroups which returns a representative from each conjugacy class of perfect subgroups.

```
load m24;
```

```
time S := PerfectSubgroups(G); → Loading "/magma/libs/pergps/m24"
```

M24 - Mathieu group on 24 letters - degree 24

Order 244 823 040 = $2^{10} * 3^3 * 5 * 7 * 11 * 23$; Base 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

Group: G

Time: 0.580

Example 2. Consider the group G of order 648 generated by the permutations (1,6,7)(2,5,8,3,4,9)(11,12) and (1,3)(4,9,12)(5,8,10,6,7,11). We construct a permutation representation of G of degree 8 by considering the conjugation action of G on one of its elements. We then construct the preimage of a normal subgroup of the image.

```
G := PermutationGroup< 12 | (1,6,7)(2,5,8,3,4,9)(11,12),
```

```
(1,3)(4,9,12)(5,8,10,6,7,11) >;
```

G; → Permutation group G acting on a set of cardinality 12

```
(1, 6, 7)(2, 5, 8, 3, 4, 9)(11, 12)
```

```
(1, 3)(4, 9, 12)(5, 8, 10, 6, 7, 11)
```

#G; →648

x := G ! (1, 2, 3)(7, 8, 9)(10, 11, 12);

x_class := {@ x ^ y : y in G @};

```

x; →(1, 2, 3)(7, 8, 9)(10, 11, 12)
x_class; →{@
(1, 2, 3)(7, 8, 9)(10, 11, 12),
(1, 3, 2)(4, 6, 5)(10, 12, 11),
(4, 6, 5)(7, 9, 8)(10, 12, 11),
(4, 5, 6)(7, 8, 9)(10, 11, 12),
(1, 2, 3)(4, 5, 6)(10, 11, 12),
(1, 3, 2)(7, 9, 8)(10, 12, 11),
(1, 3, 2)(4, 6, 5)(7, 9, 8),
(1, 2, 3)(4, 5, 6)(7, 8, 9)
@}
#x_class; →8
S := SymmetricGroup(8);
images := [S![Index(x_class, x_class[i]^(G.j)):i in [1..8]] :j in [1..2]];
f := hom< G -> S | images>;
S; → Symmetric group S acting on a set of cardinality 8
Order = 40320 = 2^7 * 3^2 * 5 * 7
images; →[ (1, 2, 4, 6, 5, 3)(7, 8), (1, 2, 8, 6, 5, 7)(3, 4) ]
f; → Homomorphism of GrpPerm: G, Degree 12, Order 2^3 * 3^4 into GrpPerm: S, Degree 8, Order
2^7 * 3^2 * 5 * 7 induced by
(1, 6, 7)(2, 5, 8, 3, 4, 9)(11, 12) |--> (1, 2, 4, 6, 5, 3)(7, 8)
(1, 3)(4, 9, 12)(5, 8, 10, 6, 7, 11) |--> (1, 2, 8, 6, 5, 7)(3, 4)
The map f is the homomorphism of G onto the group induced by the action of the element x. We
computer the images of some elements and then find the image and kernel of f.
(G.1*G.-2) @ f; → (2, 3, 7)(4, 8, 5)
((G.1) @ f) * ((G.2) @ f) ^ -1; → (2, 3, 7)(4, 8, 5)
H := Image(f);
H; →Permutation group H acting on a set of cardinality 8
Order = 24 = 2^3 * 3
(1, 2, 4, 6, 5, 3)(7, 8)
(1, 2, 8, 6, 5, 7)(3, 4)
Kernel(f); →Permutation group acting on a set of cardinality 12
Order = 27 = 3^3
(4, 6, 5)(7, 9, 8)(10, 12, 11)
(1, 2, 3)(7, 8, 9)(10, 11, 12)
(7, 9, 8)(10, 11, 12)
We now find the preimage of O2(H) as a subgroup of G.
pCore(H, 2) @@ f; →Permutation group acting on a set of cardinality 12
Order = 216 = 2^3 * 3^3
(1, 11)(2, 10)(3, 12)(4, 9, 5, 8, 6, 7)
(1, 4, 2, 5, 3, 6)(7, 11, 9, 10, 8, 12)
(1, 2, 3)(7, 8, 9)(10, 11, 12)
(7, 9, 8)(10, 11, 12)
(4, 6, 5)(7, 9, 8)(10, 12, 11)
(2, 3)(4, 5)(8, 9)(11, 12)
The abelian group Z2 × Z2 × Z4 :
A := AbelianGroup(GrpPerm, [2, 2, 4] );
A; → Permutation group A acting on a set of cardinality 8
Order = 16 = 2^4
(1, 2)
(3, 4)
(5, 6, 7, 8)

```

The alternating group of degree 12:

A12 := AlternatingGroup(GrpPerm, 12);

A12; → Permutation group A12 acting on a set of cardinality 12

Order = 239500800 = 2⁹ * 3⁵ * 5² * 7 * 11

(1, 2)(3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12)

(1, 2, 3)

The cyclic group Z_{24} :

Z24 := CyclicGroup(GrpPerm, 24);

Z24; → Permutation group Z24 acting on a set of cardinality 24

Order = 24 = 2³ * 3

(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24)

The dihedral group of order 24:

D12 := DihedralGroup(GrpPerm, 12);

D12; → Permutation group D12 acting on a set of cardinality 12

Order = 24 = 2³ * 3

(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12)

(1, 12)(2, 11)(3, 10)(4, 9)(5, 8)(6, 7)

The symmetric group of degree 8:

S8 := SymmetricGroup(GrpPerm, 8);

S8; → Symmetric group S8 acting on a set of cardinality 8

Order = 40320 = 2⁷ * 3² * 5 * 7

We define G to be the symmetric group of degree 4 and H to be the dihedral group of order 8. We then proceed to form the direct, primitive-wreath and wreath products of G and H.

G := SymmetricGroup(GrpPerm, 4);

H := DihedralGroup(GrpPerm, 3);

D := DirectProduct(G, H);

D; → Permutation group D acting on a set of cardinality 7

Order = 144 = 2⁴ * 3²

(1, 2, 3, 4)

(1, 2)

(5, 6, 7)

(5, 6)

T := PrimitiveWreathProduct(G, H);

T; → Permutation group T acting on a set of cardinality 64

Order = 82944 = 2¹⁰ * 3⁴

(2, 5, 17)(3, 9, 33)(4, 13, 49)(6, 21, 18)(7, 25, 34)(8, 29, 50)(10, 37, 19)(11, 41, 35)(12, 45, 51)(14, 53, 20)(15, 57, 36)(16, 61, 52)(23, 26, 38)(24, 30, 54)(27, 42, 39)(28, 46, 55)(31, 58, 40)(32, 62, 56)(44, 47, 59)(48, 63, 60)

(2, 5)(3, 9)(4, 13)(7, 10)(8, 14)(12, 15)(18, 21)(19, 25)(20, 29)(23, 26)(24, 30)(28, 31)(34, 37)(35, 41)(36, 45)(39, 42)(40, 46)(44, 47)(50, 53)(51, 57)(52, 61)(55, 58)(56, 62)(60, 63)

(1, 2, 3, 4)(5, 6, 7, 8)(9, 10, 11, 12)(13, 14, 15, 16)(17, 18, 19, 20)(21, 22, 23, 24)(25, 26, 27, 28)(29, 30, 31, 32)(33, 34, 35, 36)(37, 38, 39, 40)(41, 42, 43, 44)(45, 46, 47, 48)(49, 50, 51, 52)(53, 54, 55, 56)(57, 58, 59, 60)(61, 62, 63, 64)

(1, 2)(5, 6)(9, 10)(13, 14)(17, 18)(21, 22)(25, 26)(29, 30)(33, 34)(37, 38)(41, 42)(45, 46)(49, 50)(53, 54)(57, 58)(61, 62)

W := WreathProduct(G, H);

W; → Permutation group W acting on a set of cardinality 12

Order = 82944 = 2¹⁰ * 3⁴

(1, 5, 9)(2, 6, 10)(3, 7, 11)(4, 8, 12)

(1, 5)(2, 6)(3, 7)(4, 8)
 (1, 2, 3, 4)
 (1, 2)

We illustrate the permutation operations by applying them to some elements of Sym(9)

```
G := Sym(9);
G;
> x := G ! (1,2,4)(5,6,8)(3,9,7);
> y := G ! (4,5,6)(7,9,8);
> x*y;
x^-1;
> x^2;
x / y;
x^y;
(x, y);
x^y eq y^x;
CycleStructure(x^2*y);
Degree(y);
Order(x^2*y); → Symmetric group G acting on a set of cardinality 9
Order = 362880 = 2^7 * 3^4 * 5 * 7
(1, 2, 5, 4)(3, 8, 6, 7)
(1, 4, 2)(3, 7, 9)(5, 8, 6)
(1, 4, 2)(3, 7, 9)(5, 8, 6)
(1, 2, 6, 9, 8, 4)(3, 7)
(1, 2, 5)(3, 8, 9)(4, 7, 6)
(1, 7, 3, 6)(4, 5, 9, 8)
False, [ <6, 1>, <2, 1>, <1, 1> ], 6, 6.
```

Use the function NumberingMap to construct the multiplication table for the dihedral group of order 12.

```
G := DihedralGroup(GrpPerm, 6);
f := NumberingMap(G);
[ [ f(x*y) : y in G ] : x in G ]; →[
[ 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 ],
[ 2, 4, 5, 6, 12, 11, 3, 7, 1, 8, 9, 10 ],
[ 3, 7, 1, 8, 9, 10, 2, 4, 5, 6, 12, 11 ],
[ 4, 6, 12, 11, 10, 9, 5, 3, 2, 7, 1, 8 ],
[ 5, 3, 2, 7, 1, 8, 4, 6, 12, 11, 10, 9 ],
[ 6, 11, 10, 9, 8, 1, 12, 5, 4, 3, 2, 7 ],
[ 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 ],
[ 8, 10, 11, 12, 6, 5, 9, 1, 7, 2, 3, 4 ],
[ 9, 1, 7, 2, 3, 4, 8, 10, 11, 12, 6, 5 ],
[ 10, 12, 6, 5, 4, 3, 11, 9, 8, 1, 7, 2 ],
[ 11, 9, 8, 1, 7, 2, 10, 12, 6, 5, 4, 3 ],
[ 12, 5, 4, 3, 2, 7, 6, 11, 10, 9, 8, 1 ] ]
```

Illustrate the use of the function Random using the wreath product of the symmetric group of degree 4 and the cyclic group of order 6.

```
G := WreathProduct( Sym(4), CyclicGroup(GrpPerm, 6));
> G; → Permutation group G acting on a set of cardinality 24
Order = 2^19 * 3^7 (1, 5, 9, 13, 17, 21)(2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 22)(3, 7, 11, 15, 19, 23)(4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24)(1, 2, 3, 4) (1, 2)
Order(G);→ 1146617856
Random(G);→ (1, 10, 17, 2, 12, 20, 4, 11, 19)(3, 9, 18)(5, 14, 23, 7, 16, 22, 6, 15, 24)(8,13, 21)
Display the cycle structures of 10 random elements of G.
```

```
R := [ CycleStructure(Random(G)) : i in [1..10] ];
R;→ [ [ <12, 2> ],
      [ <24, 1> ],
      [ <9, 2>, <3, 2> ],
      [ <6, 2>, <4, 1>, <2, 4> ],
      [ <12, 1>, <3, 4> ],
      [ <18, 1>, <6, 1> ],
      [ <9, 1>, <6, 2>, <3, 1> ],
      [ <4, 2>, <3, 3>, <2, 1>, <1, 5> ],
      [ <12, 1>, <6, 1>, <3, 2> ],
      [ <6, 3>, <3, 2> ] ]
```

CONCLUSION.

This paper looks at how Magma is used in practice. This paper shows how to define G as a symmetric group of degree 4 and H as a dihedral group of order 8. Then form straight lines, primitive venial and venial products of G and H . The Hess group generated by permutations is considered and Illustrate the use of the function Random using the wreath product of the symmetric group of degree 4 and the cyclic group of order 6.

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4 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

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